

Calibration of Surgical Knife-Tip Position with Marker-Based Optical Tracking Camera and Precise Evaluation of Its Measurement Accuracy

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Abstract: We have been developing a liver surgery support system in collaboration with Kansai Medical University Hospital. Our surgical support system issues a warning when the surgical knife approaches a vital nerve or large blood vessel that should not be cut. It is also able to navigate the knife-tip to appropriately resect a tumor. Our system estimates the position and orientation of the surgical knife and the target organ using two distance cameras during surgery. The distance between the knife-tip and the blood vessels inside the organ is measured in real-time. In this paper, we present the details of our liver surgery support system and report the accuracy of the knife-tip positioning. The experimental results show that the position estimation error of the knife-tip is 0.3 mm and the standard deviation is 0.3 mm. The error of the distance between the estimated knife-tip positions on the neighboring grid points was 0.1 mm. This result satisfies the doctor's surgical requirement.

Keywords: Surgical knife positioning; Calibration; Liver; Accuracy;

I. INTRODUCTION

Partial removal of the liver is performed in surgery because a total removal could be fatal for human life. There are several thick blood vessels in the liver, and precision is required in surgery. Endoscopic surgery is difficult in these circumstances. Therefore, abdominal surgery is mainly performed in liver surgery.

To support surgical operations, some systems are developed and already commercially available [1, 2, 3]. These systems measure the position of the surgical tool with specific tracking markers, and navigate surgical tools to the target position and the desired orientation. These systems are mainly used for orthopedic, dental, or brain surgery. These target parts to be operated on, are almost rigid and hardly deform. The brain itself is soft, but it is wrapped in a skull, and there is little deformation in surgery. These support systems are not supposed to be used in those cases where the target parts could deform during surgery. However, the liver deforms too much during surgery and existing support systems cannot be used for liver surgery (Fig. 1).

We have been developing a liver surgery support system in collaboration with Kansai Medical University Hospital in Japan. Our system estimates the position and orientation of the target organ and the surgical tools using two distance cameras with distinct features during surgery. One camera is used for measuring the surface

shape of the liver to assess the deformation of the liver. The other measures the knife position and orientation with high precision. Our system can alert the surgeons when the knife comes close to the thick blood vessels.

Fig. 1 Large deformation of liver in abdominal surgery

Fig. 2 System overview of our liver surgery support system using two distance cameras with distinct features

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This paper describes the experiments for verifying the accuracy of the knife-tip positioning using a newly created high precision dummy knife.

II. OUR LIVER SURGERY SUPPORT SYSTEM USING TWO DISTANCE CAMERAS

Our system uses a three-dimensional (3D) model of the patient's liver. Computed tomography (CT) scanning or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), are used to acquire tomographic images (DICOM, Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) of the patient's liver before surgery. Based on the DICOM, a 3D liver model is generated using the open source software 3D Slicer [4].

Two distance cameras with distinct features are attached to the upper part of the operating bed (Fig. 2). One of them currently uses Kinect for Windows v2 for measuring the surface shape of the patient's liver (Fig. 3). The other measures the position of the knife; it currently uses the MicronTracker 3 H3-60 [5], which is a marker-based optical tracking camera and can measure the position and orientation of the markers. The specification of this sensor is shown in Table 1.

Using the 3D model of the liver, the position and orientation of the liver are estimated in real time [6]. By integrating this information, the distance between the position of the tip of the knife and the blood vessels in the liver, as well as the distance between the knife-tip and the tumor are calculated [7]. Therefore, when the knife approaches a prescribed location that should not be cut, e.g., a large blood vessel, the system issues a warning.

Special markers for MicronTracker 3 are placed on top of the knife. The position of the tip of the knife is estimated by calibrating each marker and the tip position of the knife in advance.

Table 1 Specification of MicronTracker 3

Model	H3-60
Measurement range	D240 × W200 × H160 mm
Calibration accuracy	0.20 mm RMS
Measurement rate	16 Hz
Sensors resolution	1280 × 960 pixel
Interface	IEEE-1394b, 800 Mbps
Weight	505 g

Fig. 3 Snapshot of liver surgery. Lower image shows the surface shape of the liver, captured by Kinect.

III. CALIBRATION AND MEASUREMENT OF KNIFE-TIP POSITION USING MARKER-BASED OPTICAL TRACKING CAMERA

To measure the knife's tip position from the marker, we used the calibration procedure described in [8]. The camera and knife coordinate systems are defined as Σ_c and Σ_k , respectively. The knife's attached marker and the table fixed marker are represented as M_{knife} and M_{table} , respectively (Fig. 4).

To acquire a relative vector from M_{knife} to the knife-tip, the latter is placed at the origin point p_{table}^c of M_{table} , and the position and orientation of each marker are measured in Σ_c coordinates. The relative vector P_{rel}^c in Σ_c coordinates is given by the following equation:

$$P_{rel}^c = P_{table}^c - P_{knife}^c \quad (1)$$

Fig. 4 Knife-tip position calibration

where P_{knife}^c and R_{knife}^c denote the position and orientation, respectively, of M_{knife} measured in Σ_c coordinates. To convert P_{rel}^c in Σ_c coordinates to P_{rel}^k in Σ_k coordinates, the following equation is used:

$$P_{rel}^k = (R_{knife}^c)^{-1} \cdot P_{rel}^c \quad (2)$$

Finally, the knife's tip position P_{tip}^c in Σ_c coordinates is estimated as follows:

$$P_{tip}^c = R_{knife}^c \cdot P_{rel}^k + P_{knife}^c \quad (3)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ENVIRONMENT AND DUMMY KNIFE FOR KNIFE-TIP POSITION ESTIMATION

In the previous study [8], the experiments for evaluating the knife's tip position were conducted using a plastic dummy knife created by a 3D printer, and its positioning accuracy was only approximately 2 mm. This error is directly attributable to the accuracy achievable by the 3D printer.

Therefore, we designed and created a new dummy knife for a precise evaluation. It consists of a 3D printed plastic cube with four attached markers (Marker A, B, C, and D shown in Fig. 6), one on each side of its surface and a pointed steel rod with a diameter of 6 mm and a length of 130 mm. This rod is inserted in the center of the cube (Fig. 7). No marker was attached to the upper surface. This dummy knife was designed using a 3D CAD software in such a way that the distance from each marker to the knife-tip L_{true} was 220 mm.

For the experiment, the distance camera MicronTracker 3 was placed above a flat table, facing downward. The distance between the camera and the table was set to approximately 1100 mm, thus simulating an actual surgical table (Fig. 5). A grid sheet with grid points (P1, P2, ... , P9) spaced at 20 mm was placed on the table.

Fig. 5 Experimental environment for accuracy evaluation

Fig. 6 Attached markers on the dummy knife

Fig. 7 Dummy knife with hard pointed steel rod for precise evaluation

Fig. 8 Experimental result of estimated distances between knife-tip position and each marker

V. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

It is difficult to obtain the true value of the knife-tip position. Therefore, we evaluate the accuracy of the knife-tip positioning by following two alternative evaluations.

One is to evaluate the distance between each marker on the dummy knife and the estimated knife-tip position. To evaluate this, the knife's tip was placed at each grid point on the table and its position was estimated using the previously described method in Section III. The

distance between the estimated knife-tip position and the marker(s) position $L_{estimated}$ at each point was calculated as follows:

$$L_{estimated} = \|P_{tip}^c - P_{knife}^c\| \quad (4)$$

The measurements were conducted in eight patterns in total; MicronTracker 3 was used to measure both, a single marker (Marker A, B, C, and D) and two markers (Marker A and B, B and C, C and D, and D and A). When two markers were measured, the obtained distances were averaged.

The plot of the experimental results is depicted in Fig. 8. The horizontal axis shows the measurement points from P1 to P9. The vertical axis shows the average of $L_{estimated}$ at each measurement point with respect to each marker(s). The results indicate that the average $L_{estimated}$ was 219.7 mm, the maximum error was 0.6 mm, the total average error was 0.3 mm, and the standard deviation was 0.3 mm.

The other alternative to evaluate the accuracy of the knife-tip positioning is to assess the distance between the estimated knife-tip positions on the neighboring grid points. The results shown in Fig. 9 and 10 indicate that the average distance was 200.8 mm, the maximum error was 7.6 mm, the total average error was 0.8 mm, and the standard deviation was 2.4 mm.

Observing the results, the measurement obtained at P6 has significant errors. This is because the tip position and P6 were misaligned during the measurement process. Thus, treating the observation for P6 as an outlier, we recalculated the error. As a result, the average distance was 200.1 mm, the maximum error was 1.5 mm, the total average error was 0.1 mm, and the standard deviation was 0.8 mm.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have been developing a liver surgery support system with two distance cameras with distinct features. Our system estimates the position and orientation of the surgical knife and the deformable organ during surgery. We verified the accuracy of the knife-tip position using a highly precise dummy knife with a hard steel rod.

The error of the distance between the marker(s) attached to the knife and the estimated knife-tip position was confirmed to be 0.3 mm. The error of the distance between the estimated knife-tip positions on the neighboring grid points was 0.1 mm. This error was significantly lower than that of the previous study [9], and this result satisfies the doctor's surgical requirement.

In the future, we will reduce the size of the cube

attached to the dummy knife by changing the design of the markers and conduct navigational experiments for surgical requirements.

Fig. 9 Experimental result of average distance between two neighboring grid points

Fig. 10 Result graph of distance between two measurement points

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by Grants-in-Aid for Scientific Research (No. 26289069 and No. 18K11496) from the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT), Japan.

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